

Emergency CO₂ - Low temperature catalytic methane decomposition for CO_x-free hydrogen production

Methane decomposition (MD)

reaction, also known as methane pyrolysis, allows the conversion of methane from natural gas or biomethane into **solid carbon** and **hydrogen** with high purity:

This reaction has the unique feature of being **100% selective**. Apart from allowing the **swift decarbonization of the energy**, when biomethane is used, this reaction has the power to remove CO₂ from the atmosphere as it produces H₂ at very competitive costs. This technology enables **using the present storage and distribution infrastructure for natural gas** and produces H₂ to be used locally as a fuel for electricity/heat or as feedstock for chemical industries (steel production, ammonia synthesis, reversal petrochemistry, etc.).

Considering only the price of the raw materials, H₂ from the decomposition of natural gas costs 1.9 €/kg, while biomethane-derived H₂ costs 2.2 €/kg. At the present prices of CO₂ allowances, >60 €/ton, this process saves 0.54 €/kg of H₂. The MD of biomethane removes CO₂ from the atmosphere. Assuming a cost for the direct air capture of CO₂ of 150 €/ton and for its sequestration of 50/ton, per 1 kg of H₂ produced, 0.60 € are saved in capture and sequestration of CO₂.

The industrialization of catalytic MD has been hindered so far by the extremely **fast catalyst deactivation**, which is caused by the inevitable coverage of catalytic sites by the formed solid carbon. Competing

institutions/companies are developing high temperatures MD processes involving either metal liquid reactors or reactors using carbon catalyst particles; however, these approaches are energy-intensive, dangerous to operate and display low catalytic activity.

112CO₂, a FET-Proactive project, aims at developing a **disruptive low temperature (ca. 550 °C) methane decomposition process, using abundant and cheap metallic catalysts**. Briefly, the designed reactor uses Ni-based catalysts, which are very active but need to be **cyclically regenerated**. It is expected to reach **>0.45 g_{H₂} g_{Cat}⁻¹ h⁻¹ and stable for at least 10 000 h**.

The project, which has started in September 2020, gathers some of the finest EU research laboratories and companies, including University of Porto, author of this new MD concept; Pixel Voltaic Lda., which is a spin-off company from UPorto, responsible for designing the process lab prototype; CSIC to synthesize the catalysts; DLR to develop proton conducting ceramics for efficient and cost-effective H₂ purification; EPFL responsible for the dissemination activities; Paul Wurth S.A. and Quantis, for performing life cycle assessment and economic analysis.

As explained by Adélio Mendes, professor at the University of Porto and project coordinator: “preliminary

results allowed to reach a **maximum catalytic activity of 3 g_{H₂} g_{Cat}⁻¹ h⁻¹ and proved that the cyclic regeneration allows keeping the catalyst at its maximum catalytic activity**. Initial experiments **demonstrated world-record stabilities**, using a compact reactor loaded with commercial and non-optimized catalysts.” 112CO₂ also proposes an ambitious communication strategy, aiming to involve stakeholders, investors, researchers, youngsters, and students for this emergent technology. ●

Schematic overall objective of 112CO₂.

Check the progress of 112CO₂ on www.112CO2.eu and follow EmergencyCO₂ EU on Facebook and LinkedIn.

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